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CONTENTS

MECHANISMS FOR IMPLEMENTING TECHNOLOGICAL AND DIGITAL INNOVATIONS.....	10
Shakirxodjayeva Zuxra Rustamxanovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR IMPROVING INVESTMENT PROCESSES IN THE CONSTRUCTION INDUSTRY	16
Aliyeva Zilola Mamatvalyevna	
CURRENT STATE AND STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF SERVICE SECTORS IN TASHKENT CITY.....	23
Abdikayumov Bekzod Turdiniyozovich	
GREEN BONDS VS. SUSTAINABILITY LINKED LOANS: WHICH WORKS FOR INDUSTRIAL DECARBONISATION?	29
Ataxanov Umidbek Olimovich	
ИНТЕГРИРОВАННАЯ МОДЕЛЬ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ БЕЗОПАСНОСТЬЮ БАНКА.....	34
Маликова Дилрабо Муминовна	
ECONOMETRIC MODELLING OF FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP DEVELOPMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	42
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
AN INTEGRAL INDEX METHODOLOGY FOR ASSESSING THE INVESTMENT POTENTIAL OF AGRICULTURAL ENTERPRISES	49
Sayyora Bakhtiyorovna Nazirova	
ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫЕ, ПУБЛИЧНЫЕ И ОБЩЕСТВЕННЫЕ ФИНАНСЫ В УСЛОВИЯХ ЦИФРОВОЙ ТРАНСФОРМАЦИИ: ТЕРМИНОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ГРАНИЦЫ И ИНСТИТУЦИОНАЛЬНАЯ ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ.....	53
Срождиддинова Зарина Хайриддиновна	
BLOCKCHAIN-BASED FINANCIAL TRANSACTION MONITORING SYSTEM (SMART CONTRACTS, DECENTRALIZED DATABASE, AND AUDIT TRAILS).....	58
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
FAMILY ENTREPRENEURSHIP AS A DRIVER OF EMPLOYMENT IN THE TOURISM SECTOR: REGIONAL DISPARITIES AND INSTITUTIONAL MECHANISMS IN UZBEKISTAN.....	65
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
ANALYSIS OF THE MAIN STATISTICAL INDICATORS OF LABOR RESOURCE UTILIZATION IN SURXONDARYO REGION.....	72
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
ASSESSING THE ROLE OF SPECIAL ECONOMIC ZONES IN REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH ACROSS THE REGIONS OF UZBEKISTAN USING INTENSITY COEFFICIENTS AND CLUSTER ANALYSIS.....	77
Anvarkhonov Abdulatifkhon Jamshidkhon ugli	
TECHNICAL, ECONOMIC, AND ENVIRONMENTAL EFFICIENCY OF IMPLEMENTING AGRIVOLTAIC SYSTEMS IN UZBEKISTAN	85
Jabborov Shaymurod Akram o'g'li	
Botirov Bozorbek Musurmon o'g'li	
Atoyeva Mohinur Amrilloevna	
Avazov Jonibek Azizbek o'g'li	
МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ВЛИЯНИЯ ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА НА ТРАЕКТОРИЮ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	91

Хазраткулова Лола Нармуминовна FINANCING GREEN PROJECTS IN THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN: STATUS, CHALLENGES AND PROSPECTS	97
Qorriyeva Shahnoza Safarbayevna	
FORMULA-BASED DISTRIBUTION OF INTERGOVERNMENTAL TRANSFERS TO LOCAL BUDGETS IN UZBEKISTAN: A COMPARATIVE SIMULATION ANALYSIS BASED ON 2026 FORECAST INDICATORS	103
Umidjon Pardaev Sarvar Maxmudov	
GOVERNMENT FUNDING AND THE DEVELOPMENT OF INNOVATIVE ACTIVITIES: FINANCIAL PROMOTION MECHANISMS	115
Bahriddinov Nodirbek Zamirdinovich	
FORECASTING EXPORT AND IMPORT INDICATORS OF BUKHARA REGION	122
Ergashev Mirjon Yorqin o'g'li	
A CUSTOMER-ORIENTED INTEGRATIVE METHODOLOGICAL MODEL FOR IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST SERVICES IN THE TOURISM AND HOSPITALITY INDUSTRY	130
Bakayev Ziyovuddinkhan Toshbolta ogli	
A PESTLI ANALYSIS OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE HOUSING STOCK MANAGEMENT SYSTEM	139
Mamanazarov Oybek Shomurodovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE DEVELOPMENT STATUS AND EXPORT ACTIVITIES OF SMALL BUSINESS AND PRIVATE ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN UZBEKISTAN	146
Khikmatullayeva Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi	
CHANGE MANAGEMENT DURING QUALITY ASSURANCE REFORM IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	154
Urinov Bobur Nasilloevich	
СТРАТЕГИИ УСТОЙЧИВОГО РАЗВИТИЯ ПАЛОМНИЧЕСКОГО ТУРИЗМА В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	162
Каримова Дилафруз Садриддин кизи	
E-COMMERCE AS A DIGITAL FORM OF ENTREPRENEURSHIP IN INCREASING HOUSEHOLD INCOMES	167
Eshbayeva Shahnoza Fakhriddinovna	
ADVANTAGES OF IMPLEMENTING AN OCCUPATIONAL AND SKILLS MAPPING SYSTEM IN UZBEKISTAN'S LABOUR MARKET	172
S.B.Goyipnazarov S.M.Kurbanbaeva	
ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF FIXED ASSETS UTILIZATION IN RAILWAY ENTERPRISES: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	178
Turdiyeva Irodaxon Ismoil qizi	
SCIENTIFIC AND METHODOLOGICAL APPROACHES TO ASSESSING RESOURCE USE IN THE CONTEXT OF A GREEN ECONOMY	183
Karimov Islombek Bekpolat o'g'li	
THE IMPACT OF ECOTOURISM ON REGIONAL ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT	
Samiev Siroj Saitovich Ochilova Guli Rashid kizi	
THE IMPACT OF RISK ALLOCATION ON INVESTMENT EFFICIENCY IN PUBLIC- PRIVATE PARTNERSHIP (PPP) PROJECTS	197
Khaydarova Charos Nizomiddinovna	

PROSPECTS FOR CHANGING THE VOLUME OF GRAPE CULTIVATION DUE TO THE USE OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE VITICULTURE COMPLEX.....	202
Boltaev Nazarbek Narzullaevich	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ.....	209
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
ENHANCING FOREIGN DIRECT INVESTMENT INFLOWS IN THE POST-CRISIS ERA: AN ECONOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	215
Foziljon Rustamov Hazratkulovich	
CURRENT STATE AND DEVELOPMENT TRENDS OF THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY.....	219
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna	
ITHE PECULIARITIES OF USING FOREIGN EXPERIENCE IN IMPROVING THE EFFICIENCY OF TOURIST AND RECREATIONAL AREAS.....	225
Makhliyo Umarova	
CHALLENGES OF ATTRACTING INVESTMENTS IN HUMAN CAPITAL AND STRATEGIES FOR THEIR RESOLUTION	231
Aloviddin Zayniddinov Zayniddin ugli	
ANALYSIS OF THE EXPERIENCE OF SUCCESSFUL AGROTOURISM DESTINATIONS IN DIFFERENT COUNTRIES: RECOMMENDATIONS FOR UZBEKISTAN	237
Aktamov Olimjon Abdugani o'g'li	
ASSESSING THE EFFICIENCY OF STRATEGIC MANAGEMENT OF EDUCATIONAL SERVICES EXPORT AT THE REGIONAL LEVEL.....	247
Alimova Shamsiya Abidovna	
ECONOMIC ESSENCE OF THE EXPORT POTENTIAL OF BUSINESS ENTITIES AND CLASSIFICATION OF THE FACTORS SHAPING IT: THE CASE OF BUKHARA REGION.....	254
Djurayeva Munira Sadillovayevna	
THE ROLE OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES IN THE ECONOMY OF BUKHARA REGION AND THEIR DEVELOPMENT TRENDS: AN ANALYSIS OF STRUCTURAL CHANGES AND REGIONAL CONCENTRATION.....	261
Azizjon Anvarovich Kadirov	
Nigina Djurayevna Yusupova	
IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF BORDER TRANSPORT SYSTEMS.....	268
Ikromov Elyor Ibodulloevich	
ПУТИ ИНТЕГРАЦИИ НАЦИОНАЛЬНЫХ И МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫХ СТАНДАРТОВ АУДИТОРСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ	273
Бобонарова Камола	
GREEN BONDS AND SOVEREIGN DEBT INSTRUMENTS FOR INFRASTRUCTURE ASSET RENEWAL: AN ANALYSIS OF FINANCIAL MECHANISMS	278
Suleimanov Farrukh	
ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: A COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS OF INTERNATIONAL AND NATIONAL EXPERIENCES	286
Qudratova Gulzoda Mahmudovna	
THE ROLE AND SIGNIFICANCE OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION SERVICES IN THE DIGITAL ECONOMY	291
Munisa Abdurakhmonova	
ECONOMETRIC MODELING OF REGIONAL ECONOMIC GROWTH BASED ON THE COBBDOUGLAS PRODUCTION FUNCTION: A CASE STUDY OF SURXONDARYA REGION.....	296

Turaev Bakhtiyor Ergashevich	
GENERAL APPROACHES TO COST REDUCTION IN THE TEXTILE INDUSTRY	302
Kamola Saidova	
СОВРЕМЕННОЕ СОСТОЯНИЕ ПЛАНИРОВАНИЯ И ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ВНУТРЕННЕГО АУДИТА В БЮДЖЕТНЫХ ОРГАНИЗАЦИЯХ.....	307
Саитмуратов Саитмурат Машарип угли	
A CONCEPTUAL MODEL OF THE IMPACT OF INTERMEDIATION SERVICES ON BANK PERFORMANCE AND ITS STATISTICAL RESEARCH METHODOLOGY	314
Miraxmedov Jasur Isroilovich	
EMPLOYER BRANDING IN UZBEKISTAN: HOW TO BECOME AN EMPLOYER OF CHOICE FOR TALENT	320
Doniyorova Fotimabonu Alisher qizi	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS BASED ON A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	325
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS.....	331
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
IMPROVEMENT OF THE SYSTEM OF ACCOUNTING AND ANALYSIS OF MATERIAL COSTS IN OIL AND GAS INDUSTRY ENTITIES BASED ON MODERN MANAGEMENT REQUIREMENTS.....	336
Sa'dullayeva Sayyora Nasillo qizi	
ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC APPROACHES AND BARRIERS TO THE INNOVATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF THE REPUBLIC OF UZBEKISTAN	341
Samieva Gulnoza Tokhirovna	
THE IMPACT OF EFFECTIVE UTILIZATION OF LABOR POTENTIAL ON THE SUSTAINABLE ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT OF A REGION (A case study of the Khorezm region).....	348
Kutlimuratov Mansurbek Sattarovich	
CHARACTERISTICS OF CLUSTERING TEXTILE ENTERPRISES.....	354
Asadbek Eshniyozov	
THE ROLE OF EDUCATION AND CAPACITYBUILDING IN DEVELOPING THE ISLAMIC FINANCE INDUSTRY: A THEORETICAL AND COMPARATIVE ANALYSIS	358
Abdullaev Azamat Akbar o'g'li	
THE ROLE OF 5G TECHNOLOGIES IN IMPROVING THE ECONOMIC PERFORMANCE OF TELECOMMUNICATION ENTERPRISES	366
Saidqosimova Umida Ibragimovna	
DIGITAL PLATFORMS AND THE EFFICIENCY OF INCLUSIVE EDUCATION: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	371
Kholmonov Shodiyor Karshiboyevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF INTEREST RATE RISK MANAGEMENT PRACTICES IN COMMERCIAL BANKS OF UZBEKISTAN.....	377
Seitnazarov Daniyar Bakhadyrovich	
METHODOLOGY AND WAYS OF EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	385
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
MAIN DIRECTIONS AND PROSPECTS FOR THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF INVESTMENTS IN THE CONTEXT OF TRANSFORMATION	391
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
IMPROVING THE EFFECTIVE MANAGEMENT OF THE DEVELOPMENT	

OF SMALL INDUSTRIAL ZONES.....	395
Shodmonkulov Kamoliddin Murodillayevich	
ПОВЫШЕНИЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННОЙ АКТИВНОСТИ РЕГИОНОВ КАК ФАКТОР ОБЕСПЕЧЕНИЯ УСТОЙЧИВОГО ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОГО РОСТА.....	399
Бутаева Сабина Холиёровна	
THE ROLE OF DIGITAL MARKETING STRATEGIES IN INCREASING THE BRAND CAPITAL OF TOURISM ENTERPRISES	404
Zufarov Akmal Gulamiddinovich	
ANALYSIS OF THE CURRENT STATE OF INFRASTRUCTURE PROJECT FINANCING UNDER PUBLIC-PRIVATE PARTNERSHIPS (PPP)	416
Shodiev Akmal O'ktamjon ugli	
IMPROVING THE MANAGEMENT OF THE INVESTMENT ENVIRONMENT	422
To'rayev Jasurali To'rayevich	
BLOCKCHAIN AND IOT FOR DIGITAL TRACKING OF FOOD EXPORT/IMPORT FLOWS.....	426
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna	
Najmiddinov Yakhyo Fazliddin ugli	
THE PAYBACK PERIOD METHOD IN PERSONAL FINANCE: APPLICATIONS AND IMPLICATIONS FOR FINANCIAL DECISION-MAKING	438
Akhunova Elena Anvarovna	
DEVELOPMENT OF AN ADAPTIVE FIBONACCI STRUCTURAL ANALYSIS MODEL FOR GOLD TRADING: EVIDENCE FROM THE XAU/USD MARKET	447
Tukmirzaev Kamol Mumin ugli	
DEVELOPING MARKETING MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL TRADE THROUGH A BRAND MANAGEMENT SYSTEM: DIRECTIONS AND STRATEGIC PRIORITIES.....	455
Shohboz Ro'zimatov Hamdambek o'g'li	
MODERN APPROACHES TO FORMING A COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF STUDENTS OF HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS	461
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
FORMING THE COMMUNICATIVE CULTURE OF MANAGING PERSONNEL AND STUDENTS ON THE BASIS OF A COMPETENCY-BASED APPROACH.....	466
Temirova Shakhlo Rakhmonovna	
ЭВОЛЮЦИЯ НАУЧНЫХ ВЗГЛЯДОВ НА РОЛЬ СФЕРЫ УСЛУГ В ЭКОНОМИКЕ.....	472
Усманов Фарзод Шохрухович	
STRATEGIC INSIGHTS FOR UZBEKISTAN'S RURAL DIGITALIZATION: LESSONS FROM THE SPATIAL SPILLOVER EFFECTS OF CHINA'S DIGITAL ECONOMY	481
Zhang Zhe	
ЦИФРОВЫЕ МЕХАНИЗМЫ ОБОСНОВАНИЯ НАЧАЛЬНОЙ ЦЕНЫ В ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ ЗАКУПКАХ: ПРОЗРАЧНОСТЬ, КОНКУРЕНЦИЯ И РАЦИОНАЛЬНОЕ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЕ СРЕДСТВ	487
Тўхтасинов Бобомурод Исақжон ўғли	
IMPROVING ORGANIZATIONAL AND ECONOMIC MECHANISMS FOR ENHANCING SERVICE INFRASTRUCTURE EFFICIENCY: EVIDENCE FROM KASHKADARYA REGION	493
Azimov Islom	
ASSESSING DIGITAL GOVERNANCE EFFECTIVENESS IN HIGHER EDUCATION INSTITUTIONS: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN	498
Berdiyev Temurbek Makhmudullo ugli	
РАЗРАБОТКА ИНТЕГРАЛЬНОГО ИНДЕКСА КОРПОРАТИВНОГО УПРАВЛЕНИЯ (CGI) ДЛЯ БАНКОВ С ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫМ УЧАСТИЕМ.....	506

Жумадуллаева Дурдона Шухрат кизи	
DIGITAL ECONOMY-BASED GOVERNANCE IN HIGHER EDUCATION: LEVERAGING AI AND DATA FOR IMPROVED INSTITUTIONAL PERFORMANCE	512
Olimjonov Abbosjon Olimjonovich	
THE IMPACT OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT ON NATIONAL ECONOMIC COMPETITIVENESS.....	517
Baymuradov Shokhrukh Makhmudovich	
FACTORS INFLUENCING TAX REVENUE EFFICIENCY IN UZBEKISTAN IN THE CONTEXT OF SUSTAINABLE DEVELOPMENT.....	522
Jurayev Xusan Atamuratovich	
THE ESSENCE, TASKS, AND INTERNATIONAL APPROACHES OF INTERNAL AUDIT IN LEASING TRANSACTIONS.....	536
Sadritdinov Bakhodir Bakhtiyarovich	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF MANAGEMENT ACCOUNTING IN THE MINING SECTOR.....	543
Oybekova S.K.	
METHODOLOGY FOR REFLECTING GOODWILL, INTANGIBLE ASSETS, AND INVESTMENTS IN CONSOLIDATION.....	548
Maxmudova Nargiza Davlyat qizi	
FACTORS AFFECTING DAIRY PRODUCTION EFFICIENCY: CORRELATION AND REGRESSION ANALYSIS.....	554
Ergashev M.Y.	
Tairova Z.M.	
THE DMED INFORMATION SYSTEM AS A FOUNDATION FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE NATIONAL E-HEALTH SYSTEM	561
Omonov Olim Murodullayevich	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS FOR ENHANCING THE COMPETITIVENESS OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTS IN GLOBAL MARKETS	566
Safarova Muxabbat Radjabovna	
THEORETICAL AND ECONOMIC FOUNDATIONS OF INNOVATIVE TECHNOLOGIES IN THE SUPPLY SYSTEM OF NURSERY FARMS	573
Abdufarmonov Farrux Faxriddinovich	
APPLICATION OF DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES IN THE TOURISM MARKET AND ASSESSMENT OF THE EFFICIENCY OF THE PLATFORM ECONOMY.....	580
Jumayev Bobomurod Nurmaxmat o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ «ЖЕНСКОГО» ЧЕЛОВЕЧЕСКОГО КАПИТАЛА В ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ СИСТЕМЕ.....	586
Холбаева Сабина Рустамовна	
ВНЕДРЕНИЕ ПРИОРИТЕТНЫХ НАПРАВЛЕНИЙ ПОДДЕРЖКИ ИННОВАЦИОННОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ С УЧЁТОМ ЗАРУБЕЖНОГО ОПЫТА В МАЛОМ И СРЕДНЕМ БИЗНЕСЕ УЗБЕКИСТАНА.....	595
Камбарова Шахнозахон Мирвахитовна	
ISSUES OF EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN	603
Umaraliyev Sarvar Rustamovich	
TERRITORIAL DISPROPORTIONS IN TOURISM INFRASTRUCTURE OF THE JIZZAKH REGION AND THEIR IMPACT ON TOURIST FLOWS.....	610
A.Sh. Daliev	
T.Sh. Muxiddinov	

ISSUES OF EFFECTIVELY UTILIZING REGIONAL EXPORT POTENTIAL IN UZBEKISTAN

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Abstract. This article examines issues related to the effective utilization of regional export potential in Uzbekistan. It analyzes key areas for the efficient use of regional export capacity, the level of internal diversification of territories, factors limiting the full realization of export potential in the regions, and priority directions for improving the efficiency of export potential utilization in administrative territories.

In addition, the study evaluates the impact of regional economic specialization and infrastructure development on export performance. Particular attention is paid to the role of investment attractiveness, logistics networks, and innovation capacity in enhancing the competitiveness of regional exports. Based on the findings, practical recommendations are proposed to strengthen export-oriented production and ensure the sustainable growth of regional export activities.

Keywords: region, export, export potential, export structure, factors, province, administrative territory, logistics, infrastructure.

Аннотация. В данной статье рассматриваются вопросы эффективного использования экспортного потенциала регионов Узбекистана. Проанализированы основные направления рационального использования экспортного потенциала регионов, уровень внутренней диверсификации территорий, факторы, ограничивающие полную реализацию экспортного потенциала регионов, а также приоритетные направления повышения эффективности использования экспортного потенциала административных территорий.

Кроме того, в исследовании оценивается влияние региональной экономической специализации и развития инфраструктуры на экспортные показатели. Особое внимание уделено роли инвестиционной привлекательности, логистических сетей и инновационного потенциала в повышении конкурентоспособности регионального экспорта. На основе полученных результатов разработаны практические рекомендации по укреплению экспортоориентированного производства и обеспечению устойчивого роста экспортной деятельности регионов.

Ключевые слова: регион, экспорт, экспортный потенциал, структура экспорта, факторы, область, административная территория, логистика, инфраструктура.

INTRODUCTION

When analyzing the utilization of the export potential of countries and regions, indicators such as export volume, export structure, export geography, regional export concentration, the ratio of exports to gross regional product and industrial output, as well as the number of exporting enterprises, are of great importance. Export potential reflects not only the volume of existing exports but also the ability of products and services produced in a region to enter foreign markets, comply with international standards, and be supported by logistics, customs, certification, marketing, financing, and trade infrastructure.

Strengthening export potential has become one of the central priorities of Uzbekistan's economic policy in recent years. The "Uzbekistan — 2030" Strategy sets important tasks, including doubling export volumes to USD 45 billion, increasing the number of exporting enterprises from 6.5 thousand to 15 thousand, increasing the export of finished and semi-finished products by 3.3 times, and sharply expanding the number of enterprises that have implemented international standards [2]. In official presentations at the end of 2025, it was emphasized that significant export reserves exist in construction materials, light industry, electrical engineering, food production, household chemicals, mechanical engineering, and metals.

This article selects several key criteria for assessing the level of utilization of regional export potential. In particular, the analysis takes into account the region's share in total exports, the level of diversification of the export structure, the share of processed and high-value-added products, export geography, the number of exporting enterprises, the availability of logistics and transport infrastructure, opportunities for entering foreign markets, and investment activity.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical foundations of export potential originate from the classical theories of international trade. Through the theory of absolute advantage, A. Smith demonstrated that international trade develops on the basis of differences in labor productivity and the natural advantages of countries. D. Ricardo, through the theory of comparative advantage, scientifically proved that countries benefit from international trade when they specialize in producing goods with lower opportunity costs relative to other countries. J.S. Mill further developed these ideas by examining the terms of trade and exchange relationships, highlighting the influence of the balance between exports and imports on economic growth [7].

In the twentieth century, international trade theory was further enriched by the factor endowment theory developed by E. Heckscher and B. Ohlin. According to this approach, countries tend to export goods that intensively utilize their relatively abundant and less costly factors of production [3]. In the context of Uzbekistan, this theory provides an important methodological framework for analyzing the export potential of labor-intensive industries, agricultural products, textiles, non-ferrous metals, food products, and services.

P. Samuelson further advanced international trade theory through a neoclassical analytical framework, explaining the relationship between free trade, resource allocation, and economic welfare [15]. In contrast, the Leontief Paradox, proposed by V. Leontief, demonstrated that factor endowment theory does not apply uniformly across all countries, emphasizing that export structures are also shaped by technological, institutional, and historical factors.

P. Krugman occupies a prominent position in modern international trade theory. In his New Trade Theory, economies of scale, monopolistic competition, and market size are identified as key determinants of export performance [5]. This approach is particularly relevant for assessing the export potential of Uzbekistan's regions, where export competitiveness depends not only on the availability of natural resources but also on the development of industrial clusters, inter-firm cooperation, industrial zones, logistics centers, and supporting service infrastructure.

M. Porter's theory of competitive advantage is of particular practical significance for evaluating export potential. Porter's Diamond Model identifies firm strategy, demand conditions, related and supporting industries, and factor conditions as the principal determinants of export competitiveness [12]. This framework is especially useful for assessing export-oriented industries across the regions of Uzbekistan. For example, in the Bukhara region, the export potential of the textile industry, tourism services, agricultural products, and the oil and gas chemical sector can be evaluated from the perspective of regional competitive advantages.

Within the field of regional development theory, F. Perroux's concept of growth **poles** provides an important theoretical basis for analyzing export potential at the regional level. According to Perroux, economic development is not distributed uniformly across regions but is driven by leading industries and dynamic growth centers [11]. This concept helps explain the uneven spatial distribution of export activities across Uzbekistan's administrative regions, including differences in the concentration of exporting enterprises, industrial capacity, and transport and logistics infrastructure.

A review of the existing literature indicates that evaluating export potential solely on the basis of national-level indicators is insufficient. Uzbekistan's administrative regions differ substantially in terms of natural resource endowments, levels of industrialization, agricultural specialization, transport and logistics infrastructure, labor resources, investment attractiveness, and proximity to foreign markets. Therefore, a comprehensive assessment of regional export potential requires consideration of these territorial characteristics alongside broader national economic indicators.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study aims to scientifically substantiate issues related to the effective utilization of regional export potential in Uzbekistan, assess the current situation, and identify directions for improving the efficiency of export potential utilization across regions. The research methodology is based on a systematic approach, comparative analysis, statistical grouping, structural analysis, economic-statistical analysis, factor analysis, and generalization methods.

The theoretical and methodological basis of the research consists of scientific views on export potential, regional economic development, regional competitiveness, diversification of the foreign trade structure, and development of logistics infrastructure. In this article, regional export potential is considered a complex economic category related to a region's existing natural and economic resources, production capacities, labor potential, investment opportunities, infrastructure provision, logistics advantages, and opportunities for entering foreign markets.

In the course of the study, statistical data related to export volumes in the Republic of Uzbekistan, export structure, regional foreign trade indicators, exports of industrial and agricultural products, exports of services, transport and logistics infrastructure, and the production specialization of regions were analyzed. Decrees and resolutions of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, open statistical and analytical data from the National Statistics Committee, the Ministry of Investment, Industry and Trade, the Customs Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan, as well as materials from international organizations, were used as the information base of the study.

The export indicators of Uzbekistan's administrative regions were compared using the comparative analysis method. Based on structural analysis, trends in the shares of raw materials, semi-finished products, finished industrial products, food products, and services in the export structure were examined.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

One of the important indicators for assessing the effective utilization of regional export potential is the share of each region in the total volume of exports. Analysis of this indicator shows that the shares of the country's administrative regions in gross exports remain highly uneven, with significant disparities among territories (Table 1). This, in turn, indicates that regional export potential is not being fully and effectively utilized.

As can be seen from the table data, Tashkent city and Tashkent region stand out with considerably higher export shares compared to other regions. This situation can be explained by the concentration of industrial enterprises, developed infrastructure, and relatively high investment activity in these territories. In contrast, many regions continue to face challenges related to limited production capacity, insufficient logistics networks, and lower levels of export-oriented business activity (Table 1).

Table 1

The contribution of Uzbekistan's administrative regions to the country's total exports (Year 2025)¹

№	Territory	Export volume	Share in total exports of the republic, %
1	Tashkent city	\$6.6 billion	19,5
2	Tashkent region	\$2.2 billion	6,5
3	Navoi region	\$1.4 billion	4,1
4	Andijan region	\$1.3 billion	3,8
5	Samarkand region	\$1.2 billion	3,5
6	Fergana Region	\$1.1 billion	3,3
7	Namangan region	\$722.6 million	2,1
8	Kashkadarya region	\$513.5 million	1,5
9	Surkhandarya region	\$507.5 million	1,5
10	Khorezm region	\$435.7 million	1,3
11	Republic of Karakalpakstan	\$435.2 million	1,3
12	Bukhara region	\$414.0 million	1,2
13	Syrdarya region	\$283.1 million	0,8
14	Jizzakh region	\$272.3 million	0,8

Another important direction in the effective use of the export potential of the regions is the internal diversification of the region. The highest index of intra-regional diversification was 0.97 in the Khorezm region, 0.93 in Tashkent and 0.91 in Surkhandarya. The lowest figure is 0.24 in Navoi, which indicates a strong concentration of exports in one center. According to the author's calculations, the city of Navoi accounts for 86.3 percent of the Navoi region's exports. In Karakalpakstan, the city of Nukus accounts for 50.2 percent of exports, the city of Samarkand for 42.1 percent in the Samarkand region, and the Asaka district for 41.3 percent in Andijan. This means that in some regions, exports are geographically very limited. This indicates an "island" model for utilizing the region's export potential (Table 2).

Table 2

The centralized nature of exports in certain regions of Uzbekistan²

Territory	Leading district/city	Share in regional exports, %
Navoi	Navoi city	86,3
Karakalpakstan	Nukus city	50,2
Samarkand	Samarkand city	42,1
Andijan	Asaka District	41,3
Jizzakh	Jizzakh city	34,2
Kashkadarya	Nishan District	34,1
Bukhara	Bukhara city	31,5

¹ compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee

² compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee

Research shows that in Uzbekistan, internal spatial differences between regions are very large; in some regions, exports are distributed at relatively large points, while in others, they are concentrated in one or two industrial centers. Regarding the republic, we see that the main weight is concentrated in the Tashkent region (Tashkent city and Tashkent region). These regions indicate that exports are primarily concentrated in central, administrative, or industrial regions.

One of the important areas of Uzbekistan's regional export potential is the export of fruit and vegetable products. In 2025, 2.1627 million tons of fruits and vegetables were exported, which is 126.6 thousand tons more than in 2024 (Table 3).

Table 3
Fruit and Vegetable Exports from Uzbekistan³

Product type	2024, thousand tons	2024, million USD	2025, thousand tons	2025, million USD
Total	2 036,1	1 549,4	2 162,7	2 121,2
Fruits and berries	524,1	532,0	628,5	699,9
Grapes	219,2	186,2	249,5	245,0
Raisins	53,5	79,4	113,1	143,8
Vegetables	685,2	199,8	582,5	214,0
Onions	349,6	68,0	319,0	90,1
Watermelons and melons	156,5	37,1	233,6	57,5
Mung beans	123,4	99,4	148,2	149,3

In value terms, fruit and vegetable exports amounted to USD 2.1212 billion, representing a 36.9% increase compared to 2024. Their share in total exports reached 6.3%.

The faster growth of export value compared to export volume in the fruit and vegetable sector can be explained by rising product prices, the expansion of export geography, and the increasing share of processed products. This situation indicates the need for regions to develop systems for deep processing, packaging, refrigerated storage facilities, logistics centers, phytosanitary laboratories, and export certification of agricultural products.

Another important export area is textile products. In 2025, textile exports amounted to USD 2.6325 billion, accounting for 7.8% of total exports. However, this figure decreased by 8.2% compared to 2024. In the structure of exported textile products, finished textile products accounted for 54.3%, while yarn made up 27.0% (Figure 1).

Figure 1. Structure of textile exports (2025)⁴

The decline in textile exports indicates that the sector faces several challenges related to foreign market demand, price fluctuations, competition, logistics costs, and production expenses. However, the fact that the share of finished products in the export structure reached 54.3% is a positive development. It shows that there is an opportunity to shift exports from raw yarn toward ready-made garments, branded products, and high-value-added goods based on design and advanced processing.

³ compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee

⁴ compiled by the author based on data from the National Statistics Committee

Based on the research, the author attempted to substantiate the main factors behind the uneven and decentralized development of exports across the regions. The following factors were identified as limiting the full utilization of regional export potential.

The first factor is the relatively low complexity of exports and the limited added value of exported products. The World Bank notes that although Uzbekistan's exports are relatively diversified, the bulk of export revenues is generated by products from the low-complexity segment. The IMF also noted that high gold exports in 2025 compensated for the slowdown in non-gold exports. Consequently, an increase in export volume does not necessarily mean the qualitative realization of export potential.

The second factor is high logistics and border-related costs. According to the World Bank, Uzbekistan's transportation costs are among the highest in Central Asia, with the average freight cost reaching USD 1.75 per truck-kilometer, which is 32% higher than in Kazakhstan and 23% higher than in the Kyrgyz Republic [21]. The same report identifies customs bureaucracy and border delays as some of the most serious constraints for exporters. In regional and national policy documents, the author identifies trade facilitation, improvement of border checkpoints, and development of multimodal logistics hubs as important conditions for strengthening competitiveness.

The third factor is related to standards, certification, and market entry. At the beginning of 2024, Uzbekistan joined the GSP+ system and gained the opportunity to export 6,200 types of goods to Europe duty-free. However, in practice, only 384 types of goods were exported under this regime. The President noted that the level of international certification remains insufficient, and the implementation of standards at exporting enterprises has not even reached 35% [23]. This means that a significant portion of local production has not yet reached the "export-ready" stage required for entering global markets.

The fourth factor is the low share of exporting enterprises and territorial imbalances. The World Bank report notes that the trade-to-GDP ratio has more than doubled since 2017, reaching 71.6% in 2022, but only 6% of firms are engaged in exports [19]. This indicates that, despite the opening of the economy, the deepening of export processes remains insufficient, while mechanisms for promoting small and medium-sized businesses to foreign markets, especially in the regions, are still underdeveloped.

The fifth factor is institutional coordination. Until 2024, exporters were required to pass through four border control agencies when exporting fruit, vegetable, and food products. Therefore, export control functions were transferred to the Customs Committee. In 2025, the Customs Committee processed more than 14.7 thousand declarations under a simplified procedure for authorized economic operators [23]. This indicates that reforms are moving in the right direction, although their scope and practical effectiveness across regions remain uneven. It should also be noted that in Bukhara region, the 1.2-kilometer neutral zone between the Alat–Farab checkpoints creates additional operating costs for the movement of thousands of vehicles.

The sixth factor is the incomplete WTO accession process. As of May 2025, Uzbekistan had conducted market access negotiations with 33 countries and completed negotiations with 31 of them. In addition, 13 laws, 10 presidential acts, 19 resolutions of the Cabinet of Ministers, and 10 interdepartmental documents had been adopted. The task was set to complete negotiations with the remaining two countries and form a final conclusion by the end of 2026 [22]. Although this represents positive progress, transactional risks for exporters related to market entry and regulatory certainty will persist until full WTO membership is achieved.

It is necessary to further improve regional export statistics. The open data system of the National Statistics Committee makes it possible to track exports at the regional and district levels. However, the fact that data on natural gas, electricity, special exports, and travel are not distributed by region limits the accuracy of regional comparisons. Therefore, the author emphasizes the expediency of introducing a single open dashboard that expands analysis by "goods — services — market — exporting category" across regions, an SIAT extension integrated with the Customs Committee by product and market, as well as export potential passports for each region.

Regional policy should be differentiated rather than uniform. For the capital and large industrial regions, integration into high-value-added industries, services, and global value chains should be a priority. For valley and agrarian regions, processed food, textiles, pharmaceuticals, and consumer goods should serve as the main drivers. For resource-dependent regions, deep processing, chemicals, polymers, metals, and finished materials should become the primary export drivers. A practical confirmation of this conclusion is the fact that significant reserves currently exist in the regions of the country in construction materials, light industry, electrical engineering, food production, household chemicals, mechanical engineering, and metallurgy.

Logistics and border infrastructure should be placed at the center of export policy. High transportation costs and border inefficiencies in Uzbekistan are among the largest hidden costs for exporters, as indicated by the World Bank and the Asian Development Bank. Therefore, it is advisable to introduce a "one-stop digital corridor" for multimodal logistics centers, cold chains, container terminals, renewal of the wagon fleet, permits, and certificates.

The certification, GSP+, and WTO agendas must be linked to export quality. The use of only 384 out of 6,200 preferential GSP+ items indicates a low level of institutional adoption. If the goal of the "Uzbekistan — 2030" Strategy to increase the number of enterprises with international standards is linked to export credits and

product market analysis, the export of finished products in the regions will expand more rapidly. The accelerated harmonization of technical regulations, SPS measures, and veterinary systems for WTO membership is also of strategic importance.

Financial resources allocated to exports should be directed primarily toward processing and new exporting firms. It is noted that in 2024, USD 200 million was allocated for export loans and 800 billion UZS for supporting exporters. However, it is officially recognized that these funds are not always transformed into value-added products and exports. Combined with the World Bank's conclusion that only 6% of firms export, this suggests the need to redirect financing toward new exporting small and medium-sized enterprises, export consortia, regional branding initiatives, and international certification.

It is necessary to mitigate intra-territorial export concentration. In Navoi, Karakalpakstan, Samarkand, and Andijan, the majority of exports are concentrated in a single city or district. Although this model may appear effective in the short term, it increases long-term risks. Therefore, it is necessary to launch secondary export centers, small industrial zones, logistics sub-centers, and interregional cooperation projects within the regions. This will contribute not only to export growth but also to regional employment and local budget stability.

It is advisable to develop "export potential packages" tailored to regional needs. For example, specific packages can be designed for agro-logistics, phytosanitary services, storage, and packaging in Surkhandarya, Khorezm, Syrdarya, and Jizzakh; component manufacturing and engineering clusters in Andijan and Tashkent regions; advanced chemical and metallurgical processing in Navoi and Kashkadarya; business services, IT, and professional service exports in Tashkent city; and a combination of chemical and processed agricultural products in Karakalpakstan. This approach builds upon the existing specialization of each region and moves it toward a higher-margin stage.

The author considers the following areas to be priorities for increasing the efficiency of export potential utilization in Uzbekistan and its administrative regions.

First, it is necessary to develop an export specialization map for each region. This should involve a separate analysis of each province's potential in industry, agriculture, services, tourism, transport and logistics, and mineral resources. For example, the mining-metallurgical and chemical industries in Navoi region, textiles and fruit and vegetable production in the Fergana Valley regions, tourism and agricultural products in Bukhara and Samarkand regions, and the export of industrial products, services, and logistics in Tashkent city and Tashkent region could be identified as priority areas.

Second, it is necessary to increase the share of high-value-added products in exports. To achieve this, it is advisable to transition from raw material exports to finished product exports, align exporting enterprises with international standards, and support the acquisition of ISO, HACCP, Global G.A.P., Halal, and other certificates.

Third, export infrastructure in the regions should be developed. This includes logistics centers, cold storage facilities, customs terminals, laboratories, certification centers, e-commerce platforms, and export consulting services.

Fourth, exports should be digitalized. Electronic processing of export documents, simplification of customs procedures, unified digital platforms for exporting enterprises, access to international marketplace systems, and expansion of online B2B sales channels will accelerate the utilization of regional export potential.

Fifth, regional programs for the export of services should be developed. The fact that service exports accounted for 28.9% of total exports in 2025 demonstrates the high potential of this sector. In particular, exports of tourism, transport, IT, education, and medical services can be expanded across regions.

Sixth, export markets should be diversified. Along with the markets of neighboring countries and the CIS, it is necessary to develop strategies for entering the markets of the European Union, South Korea, Japan, the Gulf countries, South Asia, and Africa.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The utilization of Uzbekistan's export potential showed positive dynamics in 2025. Export volume reached USD 33.8123 billion, representing a 24% increase compared to 2024. The key components of the export structure included services, non-monetary gold, industrial goods, food products, chemical products, and finished goods. However, several challenges remain, including the high share of gold in exports, regional disparities, concentration of export markets in a limited number of countries, and insufficient development of value-added chains.

The efficiency of export potential utilization in the regions of Uzbekistan is directly linked to regional production specialization, transport and logistics infrastructure, the number of exporting enterprises, the level of product processing, compliance with international standards, and diversification of foreign markets. Therefore, export policy should be developed not only at the national level but also based on the real economic, geographical, and institutional capabilities of each region.

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